

Impact of Poverty on Educational Access for Out of School Children in North Central Zone, Nigeria

Theresa Folashade Kolade

Department of Educational Foundations, Faculty of Education,
Nasarawa State University, Keffi, Nigeria.

Received 23 March 2025; Acceptance 27 March 2025; Published 31 March 2025.

Abstract

Education prepares children for future prospects and economic empowerment by fortifying children with knowledge and skills needed for total and general development of the individuals and the society at large. This paper examined the impact of poverty on educational access for out of school children in North Central Zone, Nigeria. Survey research design was adopted for the study which involves the retrieving of data from selected respondents representing the entire population comprising of teachers and parents in the North Central zone of Nigeria. The sample size of 800 respondents was selected from the 2 sample states drawn through simple random sampling techniques. Two research questions and two hypotheses were formulated guided the study. The study employed both qualitative and quantitative research strategies in analyzing the data. Data was gathered through questionnaire titled 'Out of School Children Questionnaire' (OSCQ). The research questions were answered using mean and standard deviation scores and independent t test statistic was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 alpha level of significance. The findings revealed significant impact of poor feeding on educational access for out-of- school children in North Central Zone, Nigeria. Thus, Feeding has strong impact on school readiness. It was however recommended among many that school feeding programmes should be initiated by state governments in the North Central States in order to reduce the rate of hunger among young children so that more out of school children can have access to good education

Keywords: Poverty, Educational access, Out of school, Children.

Introduction

Education and training are the wheel on which human ability and capacity thrive. Education is the spring of all development, it prepares children for future prospects and economic empowerment by fortifying children with knowledge and skills needed for total and general development of the individuals and the society at large. It is a prerequisite to achieve goals, develop and remain innovative. Development of human capital is feasible through education and training (Okoh et al., 2020). In deed Education tends to enhance all levels of quality and productivity.

Childhood is a decisive stage of man's development. It needs not to be compromised, as long as it remains the basic foundation of the future well being of every individual. The intellectual capacity is developed at tender age, so early interventions has great effect on intellectual capacity, personality and social behaviour of individual (Kagan, 2007; Okoh et al., 2020). Thus, child's capacity development and its sustainability sole hinge on the quality and quantity of education, which in turn depends on the type of school the child's attends. The type of future a child would get is virtually laid during the childhood stage. It is very rear for a child to rise above its education. In spite the role and relevance of education to man's development and its sustainability, many Nigerian children could not access the basic education (Nwuche and Enyia, 2022).

Factors enhancing children out of school are multi-factorial. These include poverty, parents' educational status, child's health condition, academic failure and sometime peer influence (Okoh et al., 2020). It is pathetic and disturbing to see children of school age been forced out of school because of inability to afford the school fees, uniforms, textbooks and other basic needs.

Poverty is a state of inability to afford the basic needs such as food, shelter, clothing and many forms of livelihood. A very large proportion of Nigerians are living below the poverty line, and so many are living an average life economically (Iroanya, 2024). It equally limits a verse number of Nigerian from enjoy good social life in comparison with what is obtainable in the global village. According to Amzat, (2010) poverty do endanger its victim's health, social and emotional well being, as well as their education. It is an impairment to childhoods living and likewise their futures. Amzat (2010) conducted a qualitative study to examine the effect of poverty on education in Nigeria and the ways by which it could be addressed. The findings showed that poverty restricts access to education, affects the quality of education, students' feeding and shelter. Poverty could deposed many children out of school, as the children have to cope with adult's worries and anxieties from a tender age. Poverty tends to deny its victim the chances to explore the world, develop interests and talents. In a nut shell, poverty could affects all aspects of childhood's transition to adulthood. Children living in poverty are more likely to have poor mental health and are at higher risk of psychological distress (Amzat 2010).

Poor feeding and poor healthcare can induce fear and loss of interest in school. Many Nigerian children go to school with little or no food (Iroanya, 2024). A lot go to bed without food. The hardship has caused many Nigerian children to hawk around the street to make some earn a living during the school hours, while others become perpetual street seller. Inability of parents to provide common food or basic needs of these children to keep the body, soul and mind alive is an indicator while many Nigerian children trudge out of school for survival. Children from low-income families do not often acquire the necessary stimulation to learn the social skills required to prepare for school. Major challenge(s) is the parental inconsistency to keep these children in school, as a result of lack or inadequate family income. Parents struggle to get the basic meals for these children. Thus, school preparedness and readiness is been compromised.

Feeding has strong impact on school readiness. Living in extreme and persistent poverty has a strong impact on how and when the children eat (Balasanyan, 2021). Malnutrition will definitely constitute hindrance for better performance academically. The children prefer to hawk around the streets in their quests to survive the heat of poverty level bedeviling their parents, which forced them loose focus on absolute consecration and devotion to their academic pursuit. Thus, poor feeding likely reduces the intrinsic motivation to be in school and so many children of school age trudge out of school on daily basis. Poor feeding can deprive a child a long and healthy life, accessing knowledge through education, as well as a decent standard of life.

Poverty induces malnutrition which result to some health challenge. physical well-being, appropriate motor development, emotional health and a positive approach to new experiences are enhance with proper nutrition and feeding. However, when proper nutrition and feeding can't be afforded, school readiness would be affected (Shehu, 2018). The ability of a child to succeed both academically and socially in a school environment, tends to be encouraged when a child is without health challenge. Poverty has effect on the health of its victim. Poor nutrition tends to interfere with the child's health. Poverty could deny many, the access to proper healthcare (Garg et al., 2008). Many Nigerian parents chose, self medication rather than seen medical practitioners or visiting the hospital. Malnutrition as well as poor healthcare can impair growth, brain development, child's cognitive ability and concentration in school (Garg et al., 2008). The chances of a child's school preparedness and readiness are likely to be reduced if not totally minimized. Thus, Good nutrition and proper health care cannot be compromised. Children growing up in poverty or living an average life, might experience poor health care, since they cannot afford and access adequate health facilities and treatment when necessary. According to Amzat, (2010), poverty can affect their health even before birth. Furthermore, such children might likely not survive the first year of life circle. Poverty induces poor feeding, which also can stir up illness such as asthma, and may sometime result to poor mental health.

The situation is worrisome and call for caution, as the rate of out of school children is on the increase on daily. Closed monitored observation revealed a brink future for many families and communities in the North

- Central zone, Nigeria, as many pay little or no attention to education of their children. Many children of school age are seen during school hours with bowls for begging, hoes for farm or loitering around the street aimlessly, while some are hawking around the street to sell whatever wares their parents asked them to sell, or such wares they imposed upon themselves in order to sustain themselves. Children who do not attend school have deficiency or lack of skill and discipline acquired through education at school, which will result to less job opportunities for such children. Out-of-school children are also been exposed to inferiority complex (low self esteem), stigma, and vulnerability to all forms of criminal activities in the society. The inferences of any form of out of school children are indispensable for children and the society at large. Poor feeding and poor health care impact on educational system of Nigerian children could be of grave consequence. Therefore, the study gear towards investigating the impact of poverty on educational access for out-of-school children in North Central zone, Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the the study:

1. What is the impact of poor feeding on educational access for out-of- school children in North Central zone, Nigeria?
2. What is the impact of poor health care on educational access for out-of- school children in the North Central Zone, Nigeria.?

Statement of Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.5 level of significance

1. There is no significant impact of poor feeding on educational access for out-of- school children in North Central zone, Nigeria?
2. There is no significant impact of poor health care on educational access for out-of- school children in the North Central Zone, Nigeria.?

Research Method

The research design of the study was descriptive survey research design. Descriptive survey research is used to obtain information concerning the current status of the phenomena and to describe what exists with respect to variables or conditions in a situation. The area of study was the North Central Geo-Political zone of Nigeria. The population of the study was made up of parents and teachers. The sample size of 800 respondents was selected from the 2 sample states drawn through simple random sampling technique. Two research questions and two hypotheses formulated guided the study. The study employed both qualitative and quantitative research strategies in analyzing the data. Data was gathered through questionnaire titled 'Out of School Children Questionnaire' (OSCQ). The instruments contain 10 and 5 items

each respectively. Section 'A' of the questionnaire on poor feeding comprised 5 items on educational access for out-of- school children while section B covers 5 items on poor health care on educational access for out-of- school children.

The research questions were answered using mean and standard deviation scores and independent t test statistic was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 alpha level of significance.

Results and Discussion

Research Question1: What is the impact of poor feeding on educational access for out-of- school children in North Central zone, Nigeria?

Table 1. Mean and Standard Deviation showing impact of Poor Feeding on Educational Access for out-of-School Children in North Central Zone, Nigeria.

S/N	Items	SA	A	D	SD	MEAN	STD DEV	Remarks
1	Poor feeding condition is reason for children being out of school	168	288	120	224	2.50	1.11	Agree
2	The poor quality of meals served children in families explains why they can hardly remain in school	120	248	208	224	2.33	1.04	Disagree
3	Poor feeding promotes poor mental health leading to increase in the number of out-of-school children	296	328	80	96	3.03	0.96	Agree
4	The quality of food given to children has nothing to do with their being out-of -school	154	272	190	184	2.50	1.05	Agree

5	Poor feeding is responsible for why some young children stay out of school to engage in menial jobs that can provide income to feed them.	226	334	168	72	2.89	0.92	Agree
Mean						2.65	1.02	

Table 1 shows the impact of poor feeding on educational access for out-of- school children in North Central zone, Nigeria. Results indicate that an average mean of 2.65 was obtained based on the response to the items. This value is above the benchmark value 2.50 for a four-point likert scale questionnaire. Hence, poor feeding has a high impact on educational access for out-of- school children in North Central zone, Nigeria.

Research Question 2: What is the impact of poor health care on educational access for out-of- school children in the North Central Zone, Nigeria?

Table 2. Mean and Standard Deviation showing impact of Poor Health Care on Educational Access for out-of- School Children in North Central Zone, Nigeria.

S/N	Items	SA	A	D	SD	MEAN	STD DEV	Remarks
6	The prevalence of poor health care systems especially in rural communities is responsible for why most children are out-of-school	176	400	120	104	2.81	0.93	Agree
7	Poor medical care services rendered to families explains why the health condition of most children has degenerated thereby keeping them away from school	232	384	88	96	2.94	0.94	Disagree
8	The inability of most parents to have access to affordable drugs from primary health care centers to treat their children is responsible for the poor health condition that has kept them out of school	185	370	112	128	2.77	0.98	Agree

9	The ineffective healthcare delivery systems in some communities has exposed children to adverse health conditions that has kept them away from school	320	368	56	56	3.19	0.85	Agree
10	Being exposed to poor health care services does not in any ascertain if a child will stay out of school or not.	144	200	232	224	2.33	1.07	
Mean						2.81	0.95	

Table 2 above shows the impact of poor health care on educational access for out-of- school children in North Central zone, Nigeria. Results indicate that an average mean of 2.81 was obtained based on the response to the items. This value is above the benchmark value 2.50 for a four-point likert scale questionnaire. Hence, poor health care has a high impact on educational access for out-of- school children in North Central zone, Nigeria.

Hypotheses

The hypotheses formulated were tested at 0.05 level of significance using independent sample t-test.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant impact of poor feeding on educational access for out-of- school children in North Central Zone, Nigeria

Table 3. independent Sample t-test Showing Significance of impact of poor feeding on educational access for out-of- school children in North Central Zone, Nigeria.

S/N	variables	Mean	Std Dev	Df	t-cal	Sig	Decision	Conclusion
1	Poor Feeding	2.65	1.02	1598	69.09	0.000	Reject Ho	Significant
2	Educational Access	2.73	0.48					

Table 3 shows the t- test statistics on the impact of poor feeding on educational access for out-of- school children in North Central Zone, Nigeria. It is observed from the table that the p-value at 0.000 is less than 0.05 level of significance. The result therefore reveals there is a significant impact of poor feeding on educational access for out-of- school children in North Central Zone, Nigeria.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant impact of poor health care on educational access for out-of- school children in North Central Zone, Nigeria

Table 4. independent Sample t-test Showing Significance of impact of Poor Health on educational access for out-of- school children in North Central Zone, Nigeria.

S/N	variables	Mean	Std Dev	Df	t-cal	Sig	Decision	Conclusion
1	Poor Feeding	2.81	0.56	1598	67.19	0.000	Reject H ₀	Significant
2	Educational Access	2.73	0.48					

Table 4 shows the t- test statistics on the impact of poor health on educational access for out-of- school children in North Central Zone, Nigeria. It is observed from the table that the p-value at 0.000 is less than 0.05 level of significance. The result therefore reveals there is a significant impact of poor health care on educational access for out-of- school children in North Central Zone, Nigeria.

Discussion

Findings on hypothesis 1 showed that there is a significant impact of poor feeding on educational access for out-of- school children in North Central Zone, Nigeria. Feeding has strong impact on school readiness. Living in extreme and persistent poverty has a strong impact on how and when the children eat. Malnutrition will definitely constitute hindrance for better performance academically. Poor feeding can deprive a child a long and healthy life, accessing knowledge through education, as well as a decent standard of life. Thus, when proper nutrition and feeding can't be afforded, school readiness would be affected (Shehu, 2018). Findings on hypothesis 2 showed that there is a significant impact of poor health on educational access for out-of- school children in North Central Zone, Nigeria. According to Amzat (2010). Poor nutrition tends to interfere with the child's health. Poverty could deny many, the access to proper healthcare. Many Nigerian parents chose, self- medication rather than seen medical practitioners or visiting the hospital. Malnutrition

as well as poor healthcare can impair growth, brain development, child's cognitive ability and concentration in school. The chances of a child's school preparedness and readiness are likely to be reduced if not totally minimized. Thus, proper health care should not be compromised. Poverty induces poor feeding, which also can stir up illness such as asthma, and sometime may result to poor mental health.

Conclusion

The study concluded that poor feeding and health exerts a higher level of impact on the educational access for out of school children in North Central Zone, Nigeria. Based on these results, it was therefore recommended among others school feeding programmes should be initiated by state governments in the North Central States in order to reduce the rate of hunger among young children so that more out of school children can have access to good education. Additionally, efforts should be made by state governments in the North Central States to rehabilitate healthcare facilities and subsidize the cost of health services so that good healthcare can be made available to improve the health of out of school children.

References

- Amzat, I. H (2010), The Effect of Poverty on Education in Nigeria: Obstacles and Solutions OIDA International Journal of Sustainable Development, Vol. 1, No. 4, pp. 55-72.
- Balasanya, S. (2021). Promoting school readiness through a preschool feeding program: A nutritional nudge to improve at-risk preschooler's cognitive development in Armenia. 10.2499/p15738coll2.134624.
- Nwuche, C.A. & Enyia, C.D. (2022). The Role of Education on Sustainable Development in Nigeria.
- Garg, A., Bloom, G. Walker, D., Brieger, W. & Rahman, M. (2008). Poverty and Access to Health Care in Developing Countries. Annals of the New York Academy of Sciences. 1136. 161 - 171. 10.1196/annals.1425.011.
- Iroanya, A.C. (2024). Poverty Reduction in Nigeria: A Religious Imperative. African Journal of Politics and Administrative Studies. 17(1), 857-881.
- Kagan, S L. (2007). Readiness past, present and future: Shaping the agenda. Young Child. 1992; 48:48-. ([Google Scholar](#)) ([inPaediatr Child Health](#). 12(8): 701–706.
- Okoh, C. N., Emenike J. A., Doma, A., and Akinsola, M.O (2020), 'Out of School Children: Enhancing Factors and Consequences for Sustainable Development in North Central Geo-Political Zone, Nigeria" *American Journal of Educational Research*. 8(10)

Shehu, H.K. (2018) Influencing primary school non- attendance among children in north west Nigeria.

Literacy information and computer education journal. Vol 9 (2), 2916-2922.

Publisher's Note Scholar J remains neutral with regard to jurisdictional claims in published maps and institutional affiliations.